

Self-assembly of arjunolic acid derivatives[†]

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Manuscript received 08 August 2013, accepted 09 August 2013

Abstract : Arjunolic acid, a nano-sized triterpenoid, is extractable from the saw-dust of *Terminalia arjuna*. We have demonstrated that the trihydroxy triterpenic acid can be utilized as a renewable nano entity for supramolecular chemistry and nano-science. The sparingly soluble triterpenoid became more soluble in common organic solvents on transformation to esters or ketal derivatives. Interestingly, the derivatives of arjunolic acid self-assembled in different liquids forming fibrillar networks and vesicles at low concentrations affording supramolecular gels in most of the cases. The vesicular self-assemblies were utilized for the entrapment of various fluorophores such as 5(6)-carboxyfluorescein. An anthrylidene derivative of methyl arjunolate formed a thermochromic soft-material in the presence of an electron-deficient guest. This review article highlights the results obtained in our laboratory utilizing arjunolic acid during the last ten years.

Keywords : Arjunolic acid, triterpene, self-assembly, renewable, thermochrome, *Terminalia arjuna*.

Introduction

Rapid depletion of fossil and petroleum resources has prompted chemists to orient their research towards utilization of renewable chemicals. Plant metabolites having diversified structural features and properties are the most significant renewable alternatives to fossil and petroleum resources for a sustainable future¹. More than 500,000 plant secondary metabolites have been isolated and structurally characterized. These plant metabolites play important roles in the plants in controlling their growth and developments, self-defenses against harmful organisms, coloring petals and fruits, etc.^{2,3}. Medicinal properties of the plant metabolites have been utilized for the treatment of various physical disorders since the beginning of human civilization⁴. Among different plant secondary metabolites, *terpenoids* constitute one of the most numerous and structurally diverse groups of natural products having more than 300 ring systems. Triterpenoids, the 30-carbon subset of terpenoids, are of special significance due to their rigid and flexible lengths, all measuring to at

least 1 nm in length, with different functional groups at different positions and orientations. Thus triterpenoids are nature's renewable nano gift⁵. Self-assembly of different types of natural and synthetic compounds has been reported. But, in spite of the abundance of hundreds of naturally occurring triterpenoids, there was no report on the self-assembly of triterpenoids about ten years ago⁶. Arjunolic acid **1**, a nano sized pentacyclic triterpenoid having one carboxyl and three hydroxyl groups at the opposite ends of the triterpenoid backbone, is extractable from the heavy wood of a medicinal plant *Terminalia arjuna*. The disposition of the functional groups that are amenable to several types of easily accomplished structural modifications made the molecule an attractive template in supramolecular chemistry and nanoscience.

Herein we discuss its isolation from the saw dust of *Terminalia arjuna*, the chemical route for purification and the self assembly properties of the derivatives of arjunolic acid in a wide range of organic liquids along with the applications of the self-assemblies.

[†]In honour of Professor Sunil Kumar Talapatra on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 1. (a) (i) Br_2/AcOH , (ii) CH_2N_2 , (iii) separation by crystallization; (b) $\text{Zn}/\text{AcOH}/\text{RT}$; (c) LiBr/DMF .

Isolation and purification of arjunolic acid and study of the self-assembly properties of arjuna bromolactone

Very often in nature, the pentacyclic triterpenoids having a β -amyrin skeleton are obtained as an inseparable mixture with certain amounts of α -amyrins due to 1,2- CH_3 migration during their biosynthesis⁷. On solvent extraction of the saw-dust of *Terminalia arjuna*, a mixture of triterpenic acids were obtained as a white crystalline solid in 1.5% yield containing *arjunolic acid* as the major component along with *asiatic acid* as a minor component as 80 : 20 mixture having a close structural resemblance^{8,9}. The two triterpenic acids differ only by CH_3 (30) migration from C20 to C19 and no simple method for the separation of the two triterpenic acids were known¹⁰. We have reported a simple chemical route for the separation of the two triterpenic acids via bromolactonization (Scheme 1)¹¹. Interestingly, the arjuna-bromolactone 3 self assembled in organic liquids yielding supramolecular gels in benzene, bromobenzene, *o*-xylene and mesitylene. X-Ray quality crystals of 3 could be obtained from ethyl acetate (Fig. 1g) by slow evaporation. A 1D-helical structure was observed in the solid state via a network of hydrogen bridges (Fig. 2). The observed

(OH...O) distances exhibit values of 2.851(5) and 2.920(5) Å for the double-bridge and 2.886(5) Å for the single one with angles at the H atoms of 157.2(3)°, 167.1(3)° and 152.1(3)° respectively.

Self-assembly of the alkyl chained esters of arjunolic acid

Arjunolic acid having three hydroxyl groups and one carboxyl group at the two ends of rigid pentacyclic backbone was insoluble in most of the organic liquids. We have synthesized nine esters of arjunolic acid in 70–90% isolated yields by reacting 1 with alkyl halides or alkyl tosylates in benzene or DMF in the presence of DBU as a base (except methyl arjunolate that was synthesized on treatment of potassium salt of arjunolic acid with dimethyl sulphate)¹².

As anticipated, the esters were more soluble in common organic liquids such as benzene, toluene, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-xylenes, mesitylene, chlorobenzene, bromobenzene, nitrobenzene, *o*-dichlorobenzene, *n*-alkanes, CH_3CN , CCl_4 , etc. Interestingly, all the esters examined were found to be excellent gelators of most of the organic liquids studied at low concentrations. Scanning electron micros-

Fig. 1. (a-e) Reversed-phase HPLC analysis. Conditions : C_{18} -column 8 mm \times 10 cm, mobile phase 6 : 1 methanol/water (flow rate 0.7 mL/min), UV-Vis detection at 206 nm. All the triterpenic acid samples were injected after dissolving in methanol/acetic acid mixture to obtain a sharp peak. HPLC profiles :: a : t_R (arjunolic acid **1**) = 8.3 min, b : t_R (mixture of the triterpenic acids **1** and **2**) = 8.7 min, c : t_R (asiatic acid **2**) = 9.0 min, d : t_R (arjuna-bromolactone **3**) = 10.0 min, e : t_R (methyl asiataate **4**) = 20.7 min; (f) inverted vial containing a gel in mesitylene; (g) X-Ray structure of arjuna-bromolactone **3**. The length of the molecule (30 \cdots 30C) is 1.26 nm; (h) plot of Tgel vs conc. (g/100 mL). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 11.

Fig. 2. Crystal packing diagram of arjuna-bromolactone **3**. A network of hydrogen bridges leading to the formation of one-dimensional helix is observed. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 11.

copy indicated fibrillar network structures having intertwined fibers of 40–50 nm diameter from a gel of methyl arjunolate **5** in *o*-xylene (4% w/v) (Fig. 3a,b). Similar

fibers were also obtained from a gel of *n*-butyl arjunolate **7** in *o*-xylene (6.6% w/v) (Fig. 3c). The diameters of the fibers varied from 30–300 nm for the gels of the 4-

5 : R = CH₃, 6 : R = CH₂CH₃, 7 : R = (CH₂)₃CH₃, 8 : R = (CH₂)₇CH₃, 9 : R = (CH₂)₉CH₃, 10 : R = (CH₂)₁₁CH₃, 11 : R = (CH₂)₁₅CH₃, 12 : R = (CH₂)₁₇CH₃, 13 : R = CH₂C₆H₄(4-NO₂)

Scheme 2. Synthesis of alkyl chained esters of arjunolic acid 5-13. X = Halides or sulphates.

nitrobenzyl arjunolate 13 depending upon the liquid (Fig. 3d-f); the lengths of the fibers in all cases were in the micrometer range. As the molecular lengths of all the esters were much less than the diameters of the fibers, the cross-sections of each of these fibers must contain many molecules of the gelator.

Right handed helical twist of the fibers were observed by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) for methyl arjunolate 5 in *o*-xylene (5% w/v) and 4-nitrobenzyl

arjunolate 13 in toluene (2.1% w/v) (Fig. 4). Thus, the molecular chirality was expressed even at supramolecular level with much longer length scales.

Fig. 3. SEM micrographs of xerogels : (a,b) 5 in *o*-xylene (4.0% w/v), (c) 7 in *o*-xylene (6.6%, w/v), (d) 13 in chlorobenzene (2.5% w/v), (e) 13 in bromobenzene (2.5% w/v), (f) 13 in toluene (2.5% w/v). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 12.

Fig. 4. Transmission electron micrographs of xerogels of : (a) methyl arjunolate 5 in *o*-xylene (5% w/v); (b) 4-nitrobenzyl arjunolate 13 in toluene (2.1% w/v). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 12.

Self-assembly of the ketals of arjunolic acid

The steric dispositions of the equatorial hydroxyl and hydroxymethyl groups at C2-C4 of arjunolic acid display enantiomorphic resemblance to those at C3-C5 of the D-glucopyranose skeleton (Fig. 5). This prompted us to synthesize ten ketals derivatives of arjunolic acid in one step

Fig. 5. The structure of arjunolic acid 1. The inset shows the corresponding array of three hydroxyl groups in D-glucopyranose in a projection emphasizing the correspondence of the patterns. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 13.

from arjunolic acid on reaction with appropriate aldehydes in good yields¹³. As anticipated, the ketals were less polar than the parent acid (except compound **21**) were more soluble than the parent acid in the organic liquids investigated. Interestingly, they self-assembled in a wide range of organic liquids affording fibers and vesicles yielding supramolecular gels. Transmission electron microscopy indicated the coexistence of fibrillar networks along with vesicular self-assemblies in the xero-gels of the ketals (Fig. 7). The fibrillar self-assemblies were composed individual fibers of nanometer to micrometer widths and several micrometer lengths. The average diameter of the vesicular objects formed from compound **17**, as observed by TEM in *o*-xylene, was 9.1 nm (Fig. 7). Based on the wall thickness of 4.0–4.2 nm and X-ray diffraction analysis, a bilayer structure for the membrane is supported because the calculated molecular length of **17** was 2.1 nm.

Evidence for the formation of vesicles was also obtained by optical microscopy of **16** and **23** at lower concentrations. When a mixture of a ketal in 1,4-dioxane or

2-propanol at lower concentration was treated with a solution of a fluorophore 5(6)-carboxyfluorescein (CF), entrapment of the fluorophore was observed by epifluorescence microscopy (Fig. 8).

Aromatic donor-acceptor complexes was formed from a 1 : 1 stoichiometric mixture of **20** (containing an electron-rich 4-methoxy substituent) and **21** (containing an electron-poor 4-nitro substituent). As the anthrylidene derivative **23** (which gelled most of the liquids studied) could be dimerized upon photoirradiation in the gel state, the anthryl groups were possibly placed in a sandwich-like orientation during molecular packing within the fibers.

Subtle changes in the ketal structures of arjunolic acid afford a versatile platform for achieving very different modes of self-assembly. The vesicular self-assemblies may be useful as drug delivery agents.

Self-assembly of both-side derivatized arjunolic acid

Methyl ester of arjunolic acid **5** on reaction with benzaldehyde yielded the ketal derivative **24** that was more soluble in common organic solvents than the parent acid.

Fig. 6. Ketal derivatives of arjunolic acid 14-23.

Fig. 7. Transmission electron micrographs of (a) **22** in mesitylene (2 w/v) and (b) **22** in *m*-xylene (2.5 w/v), (c,d) **17** in *o*-xylene (0.34 w/v) at different magnifications; (e) a giant vesicle of **17** in *o*-xylene (0.34 w/v) without staining showing the membrane thickness; (f) histogram for the nano-sized vesicles obtained from **17** in *o*-xylene (0.34 w/v). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 13.

Fig. 8. Epifluorescence microscopy images of **16** ($42.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) in 1,4-dioxane containing 5(6)-carboxyfluorescein ($0.06 \times 10^{-3} M$) (a-c) and **23** ($3.2 \times 10^{-2} M$) in 1,4-dioxane containing 5(6)-carboxyfluorescein ($2.1 \times 10^{-4} M$) (d-f): (a,d) under fluorescence light, (b,e) overlay images and (c,f) under normal light. Reprinted with permission from Ref. 13.

On transformation of the 2-OH group of **24** to the corresponding dinitrobenzoate ester **25**, the sparingly soluble compound was found to be an excellent gelator of alcohols and mixed solvents¹⁴.

The anthrylidene derivative **26** was not a good gelator of organic liquids. Interestingly, it formed strong gels of alcohols and chloro solvents in the presence of stoichiometric amount of electron-deficient guests such as picric acid **27** and methyl 3,5-dinitrobenzoate **28**¹⁵. In the presence of picric acid, a deep red coloured gel of **26** (0.38% w/v) in carbon tetrachloride was obtained, whose melting could be observed visually with concomitant colour change (Fig. 10). A charge-transfer band was formed at 490 nm during gelation that disappeared on melting. Control experiments carried out at different concentrations of the mixture and also with model compounds indicated the role of the triterpenoid backbone as well as the anthracene unit for the thermochromic gel formation¹⁶. Scanning electron microscopy of a xero-gel of **26** and picric acid indicated a fibrillar network structure having fibers of nano to micro-meter diameters (Fig. 11). This opens up the possibility of visual detection of electron-deficient aromatic compounds by systematic variation of the donor and the acceptor ligands.

Conclusion

Self assembly of different classes of *low molecular mass organic compounds* yielding gels have been reported during the last two decades. Among triterpenoids, arjunolic acid is the first triterpenoid utilized for its self-assembly studies. Whereas alkyl chained esters of arjunolic acid mostly yielded fibrillar networks affording gels in most of the organic liquids studied, the ketal derivatives of arjunolic acid formed both vesicular structures as well as fibrillar network affording gels. The vesicular self-assemblies have been utilized for the entrapment of fluorophores such as 5,6-carboxyfluorescein, paving the way for its utilization in drug delivery. A thermochromic material was formed from a stoichiometric mixture of an anthrylidene derivative of arjunolic acid and picric acid in carbon tetrachloride. According to our knowledge, this was the first report of color change during gelation and melting. This phenomenon paves the way for the visual detection of electron-deficient aromatic compounds. As numerous functional triterpenoids are available in nature,

Fig. 9. Arjunolic acid derivatives 24, 25 and 26 and the electron-deficient guests 27 and 28.

Fig. 10. (a-c) Color change during melting of a gel from **26** (0.83%) in carbon tetrachloride in the presence of equivalent amount of picric acid **27** : (a) gel obtained at room temperature, (b) melting of the gel at 49 °C on heating, (c) solution above 49 °C. (d) UV-Vis absorption spectra of a 1 : 1 mixture of **26** and **27** at different temperature, (e) plot of absorption at 490 nm for the gel (Δ) and for a solution (∇). Reprinted with permission from Ref. 15.

Fig. 11. Scanning electron micrographs of the dried gels : (a,b) gel from a 1 : 1 mixture of **26** and **27** in *n*-octanol. Reprinted with permission from Refs. 15, 16.

there is a tremendous potential for future research investigations on the self-assembly of newer triterpenoids.

Acknowledgement

BGB thanks CSIR, New Delhi for funding. RM thanks UGC, New Delhi for Senior Research Fellowship.

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